

DEVELOPMENT OF AGROTOURISM THROUGH COMMUNITY ORGANIZING OF TOURISM VILLAGE

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Abstract:

In planning and development of a sustainable community-based agro-tourism, which is always held the principle is the participation of local communities, Lombok Kulon Tourism Village is one of the tourist villages in Bondowoso district that successfully implement community-based ecotourism development, particularly in terms of community engagement. The purpose of this study was to describe the community organizing that occurs in the development of agrotourism in Lombok Kulon Rural Tourism. The methods used in this study are qualitative and quantitative methods with a single case study approach. The analysis finds that the process of organizing the community in the development of agro-tourism is a cycle that consists of several stages, namely: the stage of integration, mapping issues, potential, and problems, the design of joint action, activity implementation, monitoring and evaluation, reflection, and the absence of feedback to re-mapping issues, potential, and problems related to Lombok Kulon Tourism Village. The existence of Village Tourism Lombok Kulon also considered successful in increasing the capacity of community organizing Lombok Kulon Tourism Village in developing agro-tourism, when comparing the periods before and after the establishment of the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon.

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1. Introduction

Agrotourism is rural tourism which offers agricultural activities as a tourist attraction as well as the involvement in planning and management of agro-tourism area. According to Jolly and Reynolds (2005), ecotourism is a business which is done by the farmers who work in agriculture for the enjoyment and education of the visitors. Agrotourism presents a potential source of public revenue and increase the profits. Visitor's agro-tourism area can deal directly with the farmers and support the improvement of agricultural products indirectly.

One of the principles of sustainable development of agro-tourism is community participation in planning. Local communities, especially the indigenous people who live in tourist areas, can be one of the key figures in tourism, for surely they will provide the most attractions as well as determine the quality of tourism products (Damanik and Weber, 2006). Participation community is one thing that is important in maintaining the integrity of nature and as one of the alternatives in response to the demands and the urgency of developing sustainable tourism.

One approach to the development of community-based agro-tourism is the tourist village. Development of rural areas no longer relies purely agricultural sector, but evolved towards assessment of tourist activity in the agricultural sector. Departing from this, the Ministry of Tourism to create a program called Pariwisata Inti Rakyat (PIR) or to any other term, that is community-based tourism. According to PIR, Tourism Village is a rural area that offers good overall atmosphere of rustic authenticity of socio-economic, socio-cultural, customs, daily life, architecture of buildings and structures typical of the village spatial, or economic activities are unique and interesting as well as having the potential for development of various components of tourism, for example: attractions, accommodation, food and beverage, and other travel needs.

One of the most interesting tourist destinations in Bondowoso, East Java are Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Communities are empowered to manage its resources. In addition, the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon is one of the independent tourist villages – according to the Department of Tourism Bondowoso, where the management system is already well managed.

The success of community empowerment in developing of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, Bondowoso, this being one of the key community capacity building through community organizing approach; empowering communities in the planning process as a response to the urgency of planning sustainable agro-tourism area.

This research consists of five main parts. The first part discusses the background and purpose of the study. The second section discusses the literature review related to the concept of community-based ecotourism and community organizing. The third section discusses the research methodology. The fourth part contains analysis of community organizing in the development of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, regency. The last part is the conclusion.

2. The Eco-tourism Concept Based of Community and Community Organizing

2.1 The Eco-tourism Concept based of community

Agrotourism is tourism with agriculture or, *"where tourist can learn about life in an agricultural area"* (Akpinar 2003). Definition of agrotourism in the Minister of Agriculture and Minister of Tourism, Post and Telecommunications No. 204/KPTS/30HK/05 /4/1989 and No. KM. 47/PW.DOW/MPPT/89 On Coordination Development of Agro Tourism, is defined as a form of tourism activities that utilize agro business as a tourist attraction with the aim of expanding knowledge, travel, leisure and business relationships in the field of agriculture.

According to Jolly and Reynolds (200), ecotourism is a business that is done by the farmers who are employed in the agricultural sector for the enjoyment and education of visitors. Agrotourism presents as a potential source of public revenue and increased profits. Visitor's agro-tourism area can deal directly with the farmers and support increased agricultural products indirectly. Furthermore, Lobo et al (1999) explains that the development of agrotourism will offer an opportunity for local farmers to increase their income and improve the quality and welfare in line with the sustainability of the activity. In addition, through the development of agro-tourism that highlight local culture in the use of land, we can increase the income of farmers while conserving land resources, and preserve local culture and technology (indigenous knowledge) which generally complies with the conditions of their natural environments (Utama , 2011).

Development of an agro-tourism area may play a role in improving the welfare of local communities and poverty alleviation. It can be categorized as a local economic development. The local economic development strategies need to involve the rural population directly in planning, implementing, evaluating and monitoring the development of their tourist village (Yoeti, 2008). Through this approach, expected development of tourism as an industry no longer just belongs to any investor (Yoeti, 2008). Local communities, especially the indigenous people who live in tourist areas, became one of the key players in tourism, for surely they will provide the most

attractions as well as determine the quality of tourism products (Damanik and Weber, 2006).

Community-based agro-tourism requires from community members to organize themselves and operate the agrotourism business according to the rules and the division of tasks and authority which they have agreed together. Resources, especially farm land still belongs to individual farmers but each of them can only hand over its assets to the management group or management that they specify in exchange for profits proportionate. Joint capital assets they use to build the infrastructure and basic facilities are becoming a minimum requirement of the development of the agro-tourism center (Budiarsa 2011 in Saridarmini, 2011). Some of the key aspects in the development of agro-based society is a society formed a committee for managing agrowista, local ownership, homestay as a means of accommodation, guides local people, management and maintenance the responsibility of society, sustainability in terms of social and environmental principles of environmental capacity noted, technology environmentally friendly, and ecotourism conservancies (Saridarmini, 2011).

One of the approaches to the development of community-based ecotourism is the tourist village. Development of rural areas is no longer just a pure rely on agricultural sector, but evolved toward present tourist activities in the agricultural sector, departing from the Ministry of Culture and Tourism to create a program called Pariwisata Inti Rakyat (PIR) or with any other term that is community-based tourism. According to PIR, Tourism Village is a rural area that offers the whole atmosphere that reflects the authenticity of the countryside both in social and economic life, social culture, customs, daily life, has the architecture and structure of the village spatial characteristic, or economic activities are unique and interesting and have the potential for development of various components of tourism, for example: attractions, accommodation, food and beverage, and other *tourist* needs.

2.2 Community Capacity in Community Organizing

Each community has the capacity and social capital respectively. Chaskin (2001) states that the capacity of the community is the result of the interaction of human capital, organizational resources, and social capital that is owned by a community that may affect the collective problem-solving and improving and maintaining the welfare of a community. A community also is dynamic, and then the capacity of a community is subject to change. There are several factors that affect the capacity of a community, among others (Chaskin, 2001):

1. The existence of resources ranging from the expertise of each individual to the organization's strengths in access to financial resources;
2. Network relationships;

3. Leadership;
4. Support for the movement in which every member of the community can participate in collective action and the resolution of issues.

Furthermore, Chaskin (2001) identified the characteristics of community capacity as follows:

1. Sense of belonging in the community, shows the level of connectedness with community members and recognition of the state of mutually beneficial (McMillan and Chavis, 1986 in Chaskin, 2001).
2. Commitment, to clarify the responsibility of every member of the community with its participation in the community.
3. Ability to resolve the problem, namely the ability to transform commitments into action resolution.
4. Access to resources, the ability of community members to make connections instrumental in a broader context and access a variety of resources available.

Community capacity building requires intensive interaction of the components of community capacity. Of these, community capacity building focuses on the four development strategies, among others (Chaskin, 2001):

1. Leadership Development;
2. Organizational Development;
3. Community Organizing;
4. Interorganizational Collaboration;

Community organizing is one way that is needed to improve the social capacity of a community. Community organization offering social transformation as follows (Sinclair, 2006):

1. Motivating people to take action that is in harmony with the values and beliefs.
2. Connecting the community with passion and recognize the generative power of anger.
3. Bring isolated individuals who are struggling in the same conditions in a community with others.

Further, by Stall and Stoecker (1998), community organizing is a community development process that can be mobilized. This includes building a network of people, identifying common goals, and who can be involved in the action/social action to achieve the common goal. Community organizing refers to the whole process of organizing the relationship, identifying the issues, mobilizing people to these issues, as well as managing and maintaining the organization. Community organizing is also a process of building strength involving people in defining problems of a community, define issues to resolve, the solution is removed, and the methods used to implement solutions to problems such communities.

2.3 Community Organizing Process in Development of Agro Tourism Village

Community organizing is a process that mobilizes communities to achieve or do act together in the interests of the community and make an impact for the community. In the context of the development of community-based agro-tourism area, also required an understanding of concepts about the stages where the public was involved. The role of the community is also important from the planning stage to implementation and evaluation of agro-tourism activities. For organizing the community in the development of agrotourism is necessary to see to what extent the role of the community in developing that.

The process of community organizing can be improved in both individual social capitals by enhancing and strengthening relations between each other and also build trust and recognize a common interest (Chaskin, 2001). Mukhotib MD (2012) describes the stages or steps that can be taken in community organizing as shown in Picture 1. The process of community organizing is done with the involvement of external actors or party organizer who cooperates with locals.

Picture 1: Community Organizing Process

Source: Mukhotib MD, 2012

Based on the literature review above, can be synthesized indicators related to the process of community organizing and community organizing capacity in the development of agro-tourism. Indicators which became the stage or the process of organizing the community in the development of agro explained through pictures 1.

Here is an explanation of its stages.

- 1) Integration. The integration process is an important first step to ensure the initiator of the party come out of the organized people can be accepted and trusted by the community to work together. In this phase of integration should also consider the option of developing a regional into agro-tourism area to see its natural potential and other prerequisites.
- 2) Mapping Issues, Problems and Potential Related Communities Agrowisata. This step is done collectively and together with the community. Various ways can be

done to obtain the map of issues, problems, and potential of the community, such as with a discussion or a field survey and analyze the target group of the development of this agro-tourism area.

- 3) Designing Joint actions. Collective action is based on the issues, problems, and the potential for development of agro-tourism has been formulated previously. Of the discussion and design of collective action can be done in the form of consultation or meeting with community leaders who are considered to represent the community as a whole. Collective action is taken to achieve common goals in the development of agrotourism community.
- 4) Implementation of Agro Development Activity. At this stage also expected the participation of every member of the community. In the implementation phase is also a need to ensure the mobilization of resources for the benefit of the community in the development of agro-tourism.
- 5) Monitoring and Evaluation. This step is important so that the mistakes in the design of agro tourism development activities are not carried out in the future and the community more and more familiar with the steps required to improve the welfare of their communities and in the development of agro-tourism.
- 6) Reflection. At this stage, the reflection illustrates the ability of communities to look at the positive and negative values of the community in the development process of organizing agro tourism has done.
- 7) Feedback. This stage is very important to maintain the sustainability of the development of agro-tourism area. Inputs results of the monitoring, evaluation, and community reflection can be used to improve the quality and increase the benefit and welfare of the activities of the agro-tourism.

Picture 2: Community organizing process in development of the area agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon

Source: Analysis Result, 2015

Organizing the community for the development of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon is a closed process and requires a different figure in each stage. Community organizing is a form of community mobilization to undertake collective action. This process helps the community to understand the issues together, and together solve them. This process is built from social cohesion to follow along (collective action). Community organizing process aims to build the capacity to create change and development.

In the development of agro-tourism, local communities must be mobilized in order to be able to do collective actions needed to achieve common goals in the development of agro-tourism in the tourist village. Based on the review of the literature synthesis, community organizing capacity indicator in the development of ecotourism in the tourist village, namely:

1. The process of community mobilization Desa Wisata Lombok Kulon;
2. The existence of collective action undertaken to develop agro-tourism in Lombok Tourism Village Kulon; and
3. The existence of outcomes as well as the benefits received by the people of Lombok Tourism Village Kulon result of the agro-tourism activities.

3. Research Methods

In the present study has been used a single case study research approach. It is intended to look at the extent to which the conceptual and theoretical framework is implemented in the field. Research method used is a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods to answer the research goals, and then formulated indicators and related parameters according to a literature review, resulting in the survey used to collect data. Literature review conducted was focusing on the concept of community organizing and development of agro-tourism.

As method of collecting data was used a questionnaire as an attempt to answer the indicators of community organizing capacity in developing agrotourism with the target community respondents Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Tourism Village Lombok Kulon population are 81 KK, with a specification of 48 families in RT 04 / RW 26 and 31 families in RT 04 / RW 26. After a field survey and questionnaires were successfully deployed recapitulation, found that respondents who successfully obtained after field surveys numbered 61 families, or about 75.3% of the total population of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. This is caused by the difficulties encountered respondents and the limited time owned by the surveyor. However, the survey results are considered representative enough to describe the characteristics of changes in the capacity of community organizing Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The next step taken

after the collection of data is the data analysis. There are three methods of analysis used in this study as follows:

1. **Qualitative Descriptive Analysis Method.** Descriptive qualitative analysis method is used to give a clear picture of the characteristics of ecotourism, community, and planning processes that take place in Lombok DesaWisata Kulon.
2. **Descriptive Statistics Analysis Methods.** In this study, the descriptive statistical analysis method used for processing data derived from questionnaires indicator of the capacity of community organizing in the development of agro-tourism. The analysis uses the same weighting as of the relevant literature that states there is no specific emphasis or focus on each of the indicators that have been made. The expected outcomes of this research method are the existence of a description of the characteristics of community organizing capacity in developing agrotourism.
3. **Method of Content Analysis.** This method is done to address the goals of community organizing process as well as the capacity of community organizing in the development of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Results of interviews that have been conducted and the interpretation process is then performed using the data reduction coding.

4. Analysis

Education theme is a theme that was taken in the development of Desa Wisata Lombok Kulon. Tourism Village Kulon Lombok offers a variety of tours that can be enjoyed by guests; for example, include farm tours, traditional cuisine, traditional games, outbound, and social work travel. Selection of an alternative activity is also in accordance with the potential of agro-tourism and community owned. Travelers can freely determine the types of any tourist activity that can be enjoyed while in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon.

Picture 3: Comparative study in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon

Source: Observation Result, 2015

Picture 4: Farm tours for guest in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon

Source: Observation Result, 2015

4.1 Analysis of Community Organizing Process in Development of Agro Tourism of Lombok Kulon

In the process of community organizing at the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon are involved many actors, both internal and external of the village. These actors are the key to success in the development of agrotourism of Lombok Kulon. This process is carried out based on the study of literature that has been done before, resulting in six stages of community organizing. These stages include the integration stage, the stage of mapping issues, problems, and potential community, joint action design phase, the implementation phase of activities, monitoring and evaluation stage, the stage of reflection and feedback stages.

A. Integration

The first stage is the integration, which is the stage of early initiation stage between the relevant stakeholders in the development of agrotourism of Lombok Kulon. In this stage, there will usually be the organizer or initiator from outside agrotourism of Lombok Kulon. This integration phase also emphasized the importance of the smelting

process between the initiator from the outside with the local community in agro-tourism of Lombok Kulon. In the context of the development of agro-tourism in agro-tourism of Lombok Kulon this being a party outside the initiator was Mr. Sugeng Prayitno as owner Gema Art Studio Buana. Collaboration with the community is very important to create a sense of trust between Mr Sugeng as the initiator of the outdoors with community leaders at the agro-tourism of Lombok Kulon and Mr. Baidowi, Mrs. Suciati, Mr. Mulyono, and Mr. Sofyan as key person of community.

The main output of the integration stage is the existence of public confidence in the actors that will be involved in the development of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The process gains the trust is not easy given the presence of external involvement in the development of agro-tourism village. The success of the gain public confidence is demonstrated by their cooperation agreement between the people of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon with Mr. Sugeng from Gema Art Studio Buana as the developer of a tourist village. The cooperation agreement followed up with their strategic planning steps Tourism Village Lombok Kulon together with the local community. Finally, on 12 April 2011, a stage of cooperation between the Gema Buana Art Studio with the villagers Tourism Village Lombok Kulon and are characterized by their management agency Tourism Village Lombok Kulon chaired by Mr. Baidowi.

B. Mapping Issues, Problems and Potential Related Communities Agrowisata

The next step is to map the issues, problems and potential of the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The process of community organizing at this stage involves every member of the community and mobilizes them to be able to determine and map the issues, problems and potential of the community of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon in developing agro tourism. At this stage, there are a few things to note, which is as follows:

1. The existence of a natural potential
2. Readiness activities supporting infrastructure agrotourism
3. Characteristics and capacity of community groups in the development of agro-tourism

Mapping is done is not done by a certain group or developer only. This mapping should be done by all members of the community. Methods *can be* various, ranging from the discussion to the field survey. Tourism Village Kulon Lombok is done in mapping the process of discussion of issues, problems, and potential of the community. Not only that, members of the community may also be involved in formulating the common goal of developing the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The involvement of community members can be as a resource, discussion, brainstorming, through the implementation of field surveys. The involvement of community members is also to mobilize the community, which became one of the elements of community organizing.

C. Designing Joint Measures

The next step is the design of the joint action. This stage also includes the stage of community mobilization, since it takes the role of each member of the community in developing agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. At this stage, there are two things that mechanism design joint action and the involvement of community members in the design of joint action. Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, in planning an action, whether preventive or responsive, conducted by the method of discussion or deliberation. Deliberation of the agro-tourism development is done on a regular basis, ie once a month, which also involves members of the community. In addition, the meeting also held open for anyone outside the board Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Citizens can express their aspirations and participate joint action to do for the progress of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Although the new meeting high intensity ahead of their guests, but the public Tourism Village Lombok Kulon can be said to have realized the importance of discussion, democratic, and consensus building in the planning and decision making related to agrotourism.

D. Implementation of Agro Development Activity

The next stage after the successful drafting and design a joint action is the implementation phase of activities. The implementation phase of this activity also reflects the mobilization of communities by utilizing existing resources in Lombok Tourism Village Kulon. The implementation phase of this activity is more focused on the activities of travel undertaken by Tourism Village Lombok Kulon village community as a service provider agrotourism. In addition, the focus of this activity is the implementation stage roles performed by each member of the community Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Table 1 describes the division of roles for each group in the community in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The division of roles each group in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon is done by mapping analysis capability, capacity, and capability of each group to be able to contribute significantly to the development of agrotourism in Tourism Village.

Table 1: List of division of roles in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon

No	Scope	Actors	Roles
1	Internal	Women community	Handling of culinary tourism.
2		Men Community	Handling of the cultural art performances and tourist activities (agriculture and livestock)
3		Youth Comunity	As a coordinator of tourism activities as a tour guide.
4	External	Village Board of Lombok Kulon	As a facilitator to stakeholder.
5		District Board Wonosari	As a facilitator in communication forum Valley tourism

6	Government tourism office of Bondowoso	As a facilitator and help provide training related to the development of rural tourism (including budgeting)
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The division's role is very important, especially in order to create a sense of community ownership of the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon along with agro tourism activities. The division is also adjusting to the role of tour packages offered. Such as tubing tour run by the youth / Youth or arts and traditional culture which is managed by the fathers. The division of roles is also tailored to the capacity possessed by each of the groups in the community.

Beside from internal factors, there are also external actors who helped develop and support the implementation of the activities of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. These actors include governments from the village to the center. Its role also varies according to the capacity and institutional capabilities.

In general, a factor of the government is assisting in the implementation of activities in the agro-tourism village Kulon Lombok is in the form of training and development funds. The role of government is indeed indirectly and linked to the activities of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, but the contribution the government can help prepare communities to develop agro-tourism area for the better.

4.2 Analysis of Dynamics Community Organizing Capacity in the Development of Agro Tourism Village Lombok Kulon

Organizing the community is part of the capability and capacity of the community to be able to organize and mobilize the community for the creation of a collective action that provides positive benefits for the community. Ecotourism development requires the capacity of community-specific and in accordance with certain principles. The capacity of community organizing in the development of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon is an indicator of the success of community-based ecotourism development. Assessment of the capacity of community organizing is viewed from three aspects. The first is the existence of a community mobilization undertaken in developing the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The second aspect is the existence of a community collective action for the development of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The latter aspect was the outcome and benefits received by the public Tourism Village Lombok Kulon result of the development of agro-tourism. These three aspects are seen dynamic changes, ie, a period in which there is no, and the formation officially Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, exactly before the year 2011, and the period during which Tourism Village Lombok Kulon been established that after the year 2011.

Picture 5: Changes in community organizing capacity indicator in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon

Source: Analysis Result, 2015

Based on the analysis in picture 5 above, shows that, for each indicator of the capacity of community organizing in the development of ecotourism in the tourist village is increased compared between the periods before and after the establishment of the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. To indicator of community mobilization, the average number of respondents increased by 22.84%. To indicator of collective action undertaken to develop agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, the average number of respondents experienced an increase of 13.58%. And for the last indicator that the outcome is accepted by the community, an increase in the average number of respondents is 14.77%. Increasing the value of the average number of respondents for each indicator of the capacity of community organizing in the development of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon showed tangible benefits felt by the people. In addition, the village of assess their repair mechanisms or systems are being made to mobilize the community and with the involvement of every member of the opportunities the larger community.

On the other hand, the overall value of the average number of respondents for each indicator of the capacity of community organizing is still below 50% of the total respondents. This shows that the inequality increased capacity of community organizing in the development of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The new elites or leaders of this community which significantly increased the capacity of community organizing in the development of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The existence of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon thought to be still able to increase the capacity of community organizing at every level of the community.

5. Monitoring and Evaluation

After agro related activities are done, then the next stage is the stage of monitoring and evaluation. A review of the stages of monitoring and evaluation of development activities in the agro-tourism village Lombok Kulon is seen based on two indicators, namely the existence of monitoring and oversight mechanism and the continued development of agro recommendations. Tourism Village Lombok Kulon organizes monthly meeting or conference for discuss the monitoring and evaluation of travel programs. The output of the meeting or deliberation evaluation mechanism of this activity is an advanced form of recommendations that need to be done. One of the recommendations that came out the results of the monitoring and evaluation process is to improve the infrastructure supporting agro-tourism activities such as homestay, improving access, variations of games that are offered, and improving the quality and cleanliness of the environment. These recommendations need to be followed up further in order to enhance service quality agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon can be maximized.

6. Reflection

Agrotourism activities in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon have been through all stages of development ranging from integration to implementation and monitoring and evaluation of activities. The next stage is equally important is the reflection stage. This stage illustrates the acceptability of the public against the activities of agrotourism which has been running in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. At this stage of reflection is also seen their positive values and benefits for society as a result of the activities of agrotourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon.

The positive value and benefits of ecotourism development for the people of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon can be felt in terms of the transformation of culture and education for the community, improving the quality and cleanliness of the environment, and improving the economy of the community. The existence of this Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, when judged economically, have not contributed significantly to the local community. One reason is arrival of guests to Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Fluctuations in tourist arrivals that cause additional income communities of the activities at the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon be fixed.

At this time, the community has experienced a phase of reflection on the process of organizing the community in the development of agro-tourism area in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Local communities have received the benefits provided from the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The results reflect the community can be used to

redefine the issues, the problems, and the potential possessed by the people of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon related to the development of community-based ecotourism. On the other hand, there is the dualism of the vision and mission that brought by the managers of the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Dualism this vision comes from the internal and external initiators Tourism Village Lombok Kulon as described previously.

7. Feedback

Feedback is an output of the monitoring and evaluation stages and phases of reflection in the process of organizing the community in the development of agro-tourism area. One form of feedback is the development of agro-tourism area recommendations. This recommendation appears when a routine evaluation meeting of the board of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. This recommendation does not only contain things that need to be improved in the fulfillment of agrotourism services for tourists, but also contains the acceptability of benefits perceived by the public on the activities at the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon.

Evaluation comprehensively and thoroughly yet fully committed by the authorities, in this case the board of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Evaluation is done still there when travel activity evaluation visits. Evaluation of public acceptance has not been made formally and systematically. However, from there the complaints expressed by the public related to the benefits received by the public.

Dualism of the vision and mission of the parties and the board of the institution Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. This could potentially be a problem in itself. It also will affect the direction of development of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon future. These issues need to be addressed immediately in order not to cause harm, especially for Tourism Village Lombok Kulon communities. Reflection community Tourism Village Lombok Kulon has become one consideration sustainability of agro Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, both from the developers or from the internal community itself. In this feedback stage, one thing is immediately overcome the dualism of the vision and mission between administrators and developers.

8. Conclusion

The process of community organizing in the development of agro-tourism area in Tourism village Lombok Kulon consists of several stages and is a process that is closed (cyclical). The process of community organizing in the development of agro-tourism in Tourism village Lombok Kulon comprising the step of integration, mapping issues,

problems, and potential community, designing joint action, activity implementation, monitoring and evaluation, reflection, and feedback.

Destinations of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon development one of which is to increase the capacity of local communities. However, the capacity of community organizing is a dynamic result of environmental influences internal and external communities. Therefore, the capacity assessment organizing this community along with the character dynamics that capacity. An indicator of the success of the process of organizing the community in order to increase the capacity of community organizing Tourism Village Lombok Kulon there are three that community mobilization, collective action, and the outcome for the community. Overall, the average value of the number of respondents for each indicator of the capacity of community organizing in the development of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon increased when compared to the period before and after the establishment of the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon.

In defending the existence of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon, some recommendations based on research related to community organizing in the development of ecotourism in the tourist village, namely:

1. The need to strengthen the role of local governments in developing agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon in anticipation dualism vision and mission that occur in the internal manager of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. The government's role is as a facilitator to realign the vision and mission of Tourism Village Lombok Kulon development.
2. Organizing the community is also a method adopted to increase the capacity of communities at every level. Required the participation opportunities for every member of the community in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon wide as possible. Here also takes the role of a leader capable of mobilizing community members.
3. The need for equitable distribution of activities and infrastructure development activities supporting agro-tourism to overcome spatial gap between RT 04 and RT 05, RW 26, Tourism Village Lombok Kulon.
4. The existence demands for transparency in all activities of agro-tourism in Tourism Village Lombok Kulon.
5. The need for regeneration of the leadership at the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon. Prospective leaders should begin nurtured and trained to be able to mobilize the people and develop the Tourism Village Lombok Kulon future.
6. Expansion of the network through cooperation with various parties, especially parties outside Tourism Village Lombok Kulon as a strategy to increase tourist arrivals.

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